

McCouch SR, Nelson RJ, Tohme J, Zeigler RS. 1993. Mapping of blast resistance genes in rice. In: Zeigler RS, Leong SA, Teng PS, editors. Rice blast disease. United Kingdom and Manila (Philippines): CAB International and IRRI. p 167-186. ■

Breeding methods

Development of cold-tolerant rice through anther culture

H. S. Gupta, R. N. Bhuyan, A. Pattanayak, and D. K. Pandey, Plant Breeding Division, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Research Complex for NEH Region, Umroi Road, Barapani 793103, Meghalaya, India

Rice grown in the high-altitude areas of the northeastern hills of India is exposed to cold at flowering and ripening stages. It often suffers from incomplete panicle exertion, asynchronous flowering, and poor seed set, resulting in yield losses of 20-50%. In addition, due to a long crop season, only one crop of rice can be grown in these areas. Conventional breeding thus requires more time.

Doubled haploid (DH) lines are increasingly being used to make breeding programs practical (Foroughi-Wehr and Wenzel 1990). We developed cold-tolerant lines by compressing the breeding cycle through anther culture.

To incorporate cold tolerance into a high-yielding genetic background, IR70 was crossed with Khonorullo, a local red-kernel variety with cold tolerance at the reproductive phase. F_1 -derived anther culture yielded 21 DH lines of which nine were selected. We tested these in the field for yield and yield-contributing characters. All nine yielded significantly more than did the better parent. Four lines—DH1, DH7, DH10, and DH21—retained 97.5, 72.8, 87.6, and 87.5% of the yield of the F_1 , respectively. Two lines exhibited desirable white kernels, and one, DH21, had a high number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ and good 1,000-grain weight. Among the light red kernel lines, DH1 was the most promising (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of doubled haploid (DH) lines with F_1 hybrids and parents. Barapani, India. 950 m above sea level.^a

	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Grain color (p3-W) ^b
P ₁ (IR70)	145	57	5.0	123	8.1	16.8	0.4 ^c	W
F ₁ (IR70/Khonorullo)	136	85	7.0	147	62.2	23.5	8.1	p2
P ₁ (Khonorullo)	129	129	4.0	145	60.7	24.3	5.2	p3
DH1	133	87	3.8	203	77.3	22.0	7.9	p1
DH7	139	81	3.2	132	91.4	30.8	5.9	p1
DH10	130	78	3.2	77	94.8	30.0	6.2	W
DH21	140	101	4.1	159	81.5	25.0	7.1	W
CD at5%		6.82	1.01	19.4	2.25	1.9	0.51	

^aAv yield of 5 plants. ^bW = white, p3 = red, p2 = light red, p1 = very light red. ^cLow yield due to cold prevailing throughout the life cycle of the plant.

Table 2. Performance of DH lines in the field at Barapani, India.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
IR70	89.4	10.4	24.4	105.8	72.6	23.0	3.1
Khonorullo	109.8	4.4	18.0	64.8	76.2	29.3	2.2
DH1	118.2	16.0	22.0	104.8	66.0	15.0	3.3
DH7	113.6	15.6	26.4	172.3	63.1	22.2	4.0
DH10	89.0	5.4	20.8	54.4	81.6	26.7	1.2
DH21	78.2	10.0	21.4	147.6	74.1	22.3	3.3

In field tests during 1994-95 kharif (at 950 m above sea level), DH7 yielded the most (4.0 t ha⁻¹), followed by DH21 and DH1, both at 3.3 t ha⁻¹. The better parent, IR70, yielded 3.1 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2).

Yield and vigor of the DH lines are either better than those of both parents or as good as those of the better parent, possibly because of in vitro screening of recombinants. Anther culture hastened the fixation of vigor not only by fixing homozygosity but by discriminating against less fit recombinants. Increasing the sound grains panicle⁻¹ of DH21 contributed to the higher yield over the better parent. We will conduct replicated yield trials during the next crop season.

Cited reference

Foroughi-Wehr B, Wenzel G. 1990. Recurrent selection alternating with haploid steps—a rapid breeding procedure for combining agronomic traits in inbreeders. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 80: 564-568. ■

A comparison of the efficiency of four breeding methods

M. Fahim and M. P. Dhanapala, Rice Research and Development Institute, Batalagoda, Sri Lanka; D. Senadhira, IRRI; M. J. Lawrence, Wolfson Laboratory for Plant Molecular Biology, School of Biological Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom

Conventional breeding methods are successful in that they have been used to produce virtually all cultivars of small grain cereals, including rice. Their success rate per pedigree initiated is, nevertheless, low. Successful breeders must make hundreds of crosses to ensure that some promising lines emerge from each cohort of crosses.

We compared the efficiency of three breeding methods with that of single seed descent (SSD) in each of two crosses, Bg850/IR50 and 88-5328/ob255. The performance of F_6 lines extracted from each of these crosses by the pedigree (P), modified pedigree (MP), bulk (BL), and SSD methods were assessed for 13 quantitative characters in two completely

randomized trials, one for each cross. Analysis of the basic generations (P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, B₁, and B₂) and F₃ families of these crosses showed that each of these characters was heritable. The narrow-sense heritabilities of 1,000-grain weight and the number of empty spikelets panicle⁻¹ were high (0.77-0.97), and those of grain yield plant⁻¹ were low (0.17-0.18) in both crosses.

The proportion of recombinant inbred lines that could be extracted by SSD from each cross, the performance of which was better than that of the best parent, was predicted using information obtained from F₃ families. While only 3% of these lines were expected to achieve this target for panicle weight and number of grains panicle⁻¹ in the first cross, the expected proportion of superior lines was higher (8-82%) for other characters in both crosses. The actual proportion of the 100 F₆ lines produced by SSD from each cross, the performance of which was equal to or better

than the desired target, was close to that predicted for most characters.

Furthermore, estimates of the genetic correlation between characters (obtained from the SSD lines) indicated that most of these correlations were less than 0.5. Where they were larger, this was generally favorable to the breeder. Exceptions were from the expected correlations between, for example, grain yield and its components. Both of these pedigrees, therefore, had considerable potential in their ability to produce superior recombinant inbred lines. This was not only for their single character performance, but also for the desired multiple phenotype.

The average performance of the lines produced by the conventional methods was higher in both crosses than that of the SSD lines for grain yield plant⁻¹ and number of grains panicle⁻¹. Comparison of the best lines produced by each of the four methods for each character, however, showed that little difference existed between them for

grain yield or its components. The effect of the selection carried out during inbreeding with the P, MP, and BL methods was to cull low-yielding genotypes rather than to retain high-yielding material, despite attempts to do so.

The average per line cost of producing the best SSD lines was only US\$13.70 compared with US\$89.50 for the P method, US\$69.70 for the MP method, and US\$22.30 for the BL method. The SSD method is also more rapid if three generations can be raised per annum at high densities in the nursery.

These results are consistent with quantitative genetics theory, which indicates that attempts to carry out indirect selection visually of characters of low to intermediate heritability during inbreeding are unlikely to be successful. It is better to defer selection until homozygous material can be raised in a randomized trial in which characters of interest can be measured directly. ■

A promising dwarf rice mutant induced through gamma irradiation

N. R. Bai, R. Devika, and A. Regina, Rice Research Station (RRS), Moncompu, Kerala, India

M01.20-19-4 (IET13981) is a dwarf medium-duration mutant, developed

through gamma irradiation of local rice cultivar Chettivirippu. This cultivar is tall and susceptible to lodging. Its average yield is 2.5 t ha⁻¹, and it is highly resistant to brown planthopper, stem borer, gall midge, blast, sheath blight, and sheath rot. The mutant is shorter, more resistant to lodging, and higher yielding than the parent variety (see table).

We selected plants up to the M₇ generation, after which the stable mutant, M01.20-19-4, was included in yield trials (see table).

M01.20-19-4 is suitable for cultivation in all of the rice-growing seasons of Kerala, and the people prefer its red grain.

The mutant will be proposed for release shortly. ■

Characteristics, comparative grain yield and pest and disease scores of mutant M01.20-19-4 and parent variety. India, 1989-94.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Productive tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)						Insect-disease score (0-9)					
				CYT ^a (3 seasons) 1989-90	RRS Mon-compu (4 seasons) 1990-92	MLT ^b		AICRIP ^c trials		Brown plant-hopper	Gall midge	Stem borer	Blast	Sheath blight	Sheath rot
						Research stations (5 locations) 1992	Farmers' fields (9 locations) 1992	(17 locations) 1993	(16 locations) 1994						
M01.20-19-4 (IET13981)	98	120	7	4.2	3.5	4.6	5.2	4.8	4.4	2.2	2.8	2.2	2.8	1.5	1.9
Chettivirippu	120	110	5	2.7	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.7	2.9	2.6
MO5	-	-	-	-	2.9	3.6	4.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ratna	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.0	4.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ptb33 (resistant check)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.1	2.5	3.5	2.1	2.0	2.0
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.0	9.0	8.5	9.0	9.0	8.0
CD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.42	0.40	ns	0.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aCYT = comparative yield trial with 7 entries. ^bMLT = multilocation trials with 7 entries. ^cAICRIP = All India Coordinated Trials; 1993, 68 entries; 1994, 64 entries.